

Activities and Essential Strategies of Library for Enhancing Level of Media Literacy with Emerging Trends in Digital Age and Empowering UG Students of Academic College Located in Rural Area of West Bengal, India: An Assessment

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In one line, media literacy means concern about misinformation, bad effect of false information spread from media. Young generations are future of the nation. They should know about all things about digital media. And these should be started from their academic institutions. Best planning should be initiated for the young generation protecting from false information. This study aims to identify the level of media literacy among 180 numbers students of under graduate level studying in Vidyanagar College and who are using Vidyanagar College Library. This study reveals that much more path should be passed by both students and authorities of this institution.

JEL Classification Number: D83, L82**Keywords:** media, media literacy, library, print media, electronic media, social media

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1. Introduction

At the college level, students are not concentrated only on education. They spend time in other social works and activities also. In the present time, the young generation is engaged more time in social media. They are watching all things which are available on the social media platform. Sometimes, it can be seen that two controversial reports are running simultaneously. But which is right – which is reliable. The young generation should have enough knowledge to detect the correct news or information. So, media literacy is important. This literacy is not only for social media; this is same essential for other print, electronic media also.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

NEP 2020 (National Education Policy 2020) was introduced by the Ministry of Education in India. India Government enforced education digitally i.e. online learning by implementing NEP 2020. This policy says to try for providing quality education for all and highlights the importance of digital literacy and online learning. As per this order or advisory, academic libraries are trying to provide services to access the digital resources and tools by using digital technologies. Libraries can also provide training and support to students to develop digital literacy skills. For achieving the goal of NEP 2020, the gap between services available in library and demand for digital resources by library users needs to be traced for minimizing. After five years of NEP 2020 in India, the level of digital literacy i.e. awareness about ICT tools and technologies among students needs to be assessed.

Beside these, college students are not busy with their printed text books and electronic books, etc. They are also willing to search other things like social, political, etc. related issues. But they cannot able to handle all things like media stories, media trial, etc. So, now it is a right time to assess the media literacy among the new generation.

2. Objectives of the Study

Before the planning the future strategies and discussing about existing activities of an institution, and to know the actual current picture, a detailed study or survey needs to be conducted. Objectives of this study are given below:

- To find out the patterns of media usage among the students of Vidyanagar College
- To identify the level of media literacy among students who are using Vidyanagar College Library
- To know the future planning of the College and College Library

3. Literature Review

Before starting this study, the author intended to consult with similar literatures (i.e. survey conducted to know current scenario of media literacy) which are easily available.

Chaudhuri (2025) conducted a survey with 121 respondents of 16 to 35 age group. Raulo (2024) studied with 428 respondents of all age groups resided in Ganjam district of Odisha. Thouba (2024) conducted a survey on 388 Meitei Pangal Youth of Manipur. Nongkesh (2023) surveyed with 120 college students of Shillong. Sachdeva (2022) conducted a survey among 600 students of universities of Delhi. Chanda (2021) studied with 158 students of 7 universities of North Eastern India. Boruah (2019) surveyed among PG students and faculty members of the media communication discipline of Assam. Dutta (2019) studied among adult media users of Assam. Sharma (2019) conducted a survey for investigation among XI and XII class students of school of Delhi. Uniyal (2018) surveyed among 1054 UG, PG, PhD students of 3 IITs of North India. Sudha (2014) studied with 1120 users of rural libraries of Dindigul district of Tami Nadu. Patil (2008) conducted a survey on electronic media only among 475 research scholars and university librarians of Karnataka.

3.1 Research Gap

There are almost 12 literatures that are related with detailed study on media literacy. But there is no such study has been done among students coming from rural areas of West Bengal.

4. Methodology

Data is collected through interview method (with printed questions) from randomly selected sample sixty students (30 male and 30 female) from each discipline - Arts, Commerce, and Science - resulting in a total of 180 students (90 male and 90 female) from Vidyanagar College, South 24 Parganas, during the study period from July 2024 to June 2025.

This research work is a library-oriented study. So, this study is concentrated on only those students who are using the library frequently. Students, who are not using the library, cannot give opinions about activities of the library. Two librarians are working in this college library. Data or information about the library is collected from the librarians by taking interview. Some data were also collected from various registers maintained in this college and library by observation method.

5. Media Literacy and Library: Relation in Brief

College authority and college library authority have enough role to literate students about this digital atmosphere. Because in the digital world, anyone can upload any news without any restriction. They intentionally or unintentionally are doing this continuously. This may give good or bad impact on society. The new generation has low media literacy, and as a result they may be influenced in wrong way. To prevent this and to protect the students, college authority and college library authority should take initiatives to literate the students about media, fake news, wrong information, etc.

Only librarians can say the correct and appropriate answer in between a hundred results of any information search. So, it is needed to know that is students aware about fake news or not and do they feel any importance of college library to grow media literacy skill, are they dependent on college and college library, etc.

6. Data Collection and Analysis

Collected data are first presented in table form and then calculated percentage (percentage values are calculated with respect to 180 i.e. total numbers of respondents and displayed in bracket) to know difference between different disciplines and for comparative analysis.

6.1 Activities of Vidyanagar College and Vidyanagar College Library for Media Literacy among Students

Table 1: Distribution of Library Services provided in Vidyanagar College Library by Using Different Media Formats

Purpose	Through Print Media	Through Electronic Media
Academic Purposes	Books, Journals, Maps, Previous Year Examination Question Papers	e-Books, e-Journals, e-Classroom, CDs, DVDs, Digitized Question Papers
Current Affairs	Books, Newspapers, Magazines	Online news portals
Career Guidance	'Employment News', 'Kamakhshetra', 'Peshaprabesh'	Electronic resources

Table 1 shows that Vidyanagar College Library provides library materials by using both print and digital media. According to the users' demand, librarians of this library are trying to aware about information literacy for both print and electronic media.

6.2 Analysis with Students' Opinion

Table 2: Distribution of Respondents According to Spend More Time

Discipline with Respondents Number	Gender	Information Source							
		Book	Journal	e-Book	e-Journal	Newspaper	Radio	TV	Social Media
Arts 60	M 30	0 (00.00)	0 (00.00)	1 (0.56)	0 (00.00)	8 (4.44)	0 (00.00)	5 (2.78)	16 (8.89)
	F 30	2 (1.11)	1 (0.56)	0 (00.00)	0 (00.00)	4 (2.22)	1 (0.56)	12 (6.67)	10 (5.56)
Commerce 60	M 30	0 (00.00)	0 (00.00)	1 (0.56)	0 (00.00)	10 (5.56)	0 (00.00)	6 (3.89)	12 (6.67)
	F 30	1 (0.56)	0 (00.00)	0 (0.56)	0 (00.00)	8 (4.44)	0 (00.00)	7 (3.33)	14 (7.78)
Science 60	M 30	1 (0.56)	3 (1.67)	1 (0.56)	0 (00.00)	3 (1.67)	0 (00.00)	3 (3.89)	15 (8.33)
	F 30	0 (00.00)	2 (1.11)	1 (0.56)	0 (00.00)	8 (4.44)	1 (0.56)	3 (1.67)	15 (8.33)
Total 180	M 90	1 (0.56)	3 (1.67)	3 (1.67)	0 (00.00)	21 (11.67)	0 (00.00)	19 (10.56)	43 (23.89)
	F 90	3 (1.67)	3 (1.67)	2 (1.11)	0 (00.00)	20 (11.11)	2 (1.11)	21 (11.67)	39 (21.67)

Figure 1: Distribution of Respondents According to Spend More Time

Table 2 and Figure 1 show that majority of students usually spent their time with newspaper reading, TV (Television) watching and busy with social media.

Table 3: Distribution of Respondents According to Media Preference as Information Source

Discipline with Respondents Number	Gender	Media				
		Newspaper	Radio	TV	Library Website	Social Media
Arts 60	M 30	4 (2.22)	0 (00.00)	10 (5.56)	0 (00.00)	16 (8.89)
	F 30	5 (2.78)	1 (0.56)	14 (7.78)	0 (00.00)	10 (5.56)
Commerce 60	M 30	6 (3.33)	0 (00.00)	12 (6.67)	0 (00.00)	12 (6.67)
	F 30	3 (1.67)	0 (00.00)	13 (7.22)	0 (00.00)	14 (7.78)
Science 60	M 30	3 (1.67)	0 (00.00)	12 (6.67)	0 (00.00)	15 (8.33)
	F 30	6 (3.33)	1 (0.56)	3 (1.67)	0 (00.00)	20 (11.11)
Total 180	M 90	13 (7.22)	0 (00.00)	34 (18.89)	0 (00.00)	43 (23.89)
	F 90	14 (7.78)	2 (1.11)	30 (16.67)	0 (00.00)	44 (24.44)

Figure 2: Distribution of Respondents According to Media Preference as Information Source

Table 3 and Figure 2 show that majority of students preferred newspaper, TV and social media as information sources during collection of required information.

Table 4: Distribution of Respondents According to Access Media as Reliable Information Source

Discipline with Respondents Number	Gender	Media				
		Newspaper	Radio	TV	Library Website	Social Media
Arts 60	M 30	20 (11.11)	1 (0.56)	7 (3.89)	0 (00.00)	2 (1.11)
	F 30	12 (6.67)	2 (1.11)	10 (5.56)	1 (0.56)	5 (2.78)
Commerce 60	M 30	10 (5.56)	0 (00.00)	12 (6.67)	0 (00.00)	8 (4.44)
	F 30	8 (4.44)	0 (00.00)	19 (10.56)	0 (00.00)	3 (1.67)
Science 60	M 30	3 (1.67)	1 (0.56)	22 (12.22)	2 (1.11)	2 (1.11)
	F 30	7 (3.89)	1 (0.56)	17 (9.44)	2 (1.11)	3 (1.67)
Total 180	M 90	33 (18.33)	2 (1.11)	41 (22.78)	2 (1.11)	12 (6.67)
	F 90	27 (15.00)	3 (1.67)	46 (25.56)	3 (1.67)	11 (6.11)

Figure 3: Distribution of Respondents According to Access Media as Reliable Information Source

According to Table 4 and Figure 3, it can be said that the respondents usually access newspaper and TV. They also used social media but it is much lesser than newspaper and TV.

Table 5: Distribution of Respondents According to Place of Sourceas Information Centre Usually Used by Them

Discipline with Respondents Number	Gender	Information Centre				
		Local Club	Home	Friend Gathering	Classroom	Library
Arts 60	M 30	5 (2.78)	5 (2.78)	15 (8.33)	22 (12.22)	10 (5.56)
	F 30	2 (1.11)	8 (4.44)	20 (11.11)	15 (8.33)	12 (6.67)
Commerce 60	M 30	15 (8.33)	12 (6.67)	28 (15.56)	16 (8.89)	6 (3.33)
	F 30	8 (4.44)	10 (5.56)	29 (16.11)	20 (11.11)	22 (12.22)
Science 60	M 30	5 (2.78)	7 (3.89)	12 (6.67)	28 (15.56)	9 (5.55)
	F 30	1 (0.56)	13 (7.22)	22 (12.22)	30 (16.67)	19 (10.56)
Total 180	M 90	25 (13.89)	24 (13.33)	55 (30.56)	66 (36.67)	25 (13.89)
	F 90	11 (6.11)	31 (17.22)	71 (39.44)	65 (36.11)	53 (29.44)
Total 180	M+F 180	36 (20.00)	55 (30.56)	126 (70.00)	131 (72.78)	78 (43.33)

Respondents are allowed to select multiple options

Figure 4: Distribution of Respondents According to Place of Sourceas Information Centre Usually Used by Them

Table 5 and Figure 4 show that here we can find mixed opinion, because as per opinion of respondents, they can get information from all sources like, local club, classroom, library, etc.

Table 6: Distribution of Respondents According Opinion about Issues Attract Attention

Discipline with Respondents Number	Gender	Issues				
		Local Issue	Religious Issue	National Issue	International Issue	Fun
Arts 60	M 30	22 (12.22)	8 (4.44)	25 (13.89)	12 (6.67)	12 (6.67)
	F 30	18 (10.00)	0 (00.00)	30 (16.67)	29 (16.11)	8 (4.44)
Commerce 60	M 30	23 (12.78)	2 (1.11)	29 (16.11)	30 (16.67)	10 (5.56)
	F 30	25 (13.89)	1 (0.56)	27 (15.00)	25 (13.89)	20 (11.11)
Science 60	M 30	30 (16.67)	0 (00.00)	30 (16.67)	19 (10.56)	2 (1.11)
	F 30	27 (15.00)	0 (00.00)	30 (16.67)	11 (6.11)	17 (9.44)
Total 180	M 90	75 (44.66)	10 (5.56)	84 (46.67)	61 (33.89)	24 (13.33)
	F 90	70 (38.89)	1 (0.56)	87 (48.33)	65 (36.11)	45 (25.00)
Total 180	M+F 180	145 (80.56)	11 (6.11)	171 (95.00)	126 (70.00)	69 (38.33)

Respondents are allowed to select multiple options

Figure 5: Distribution of Respondents According to Opinion about Issues Attract Attention

Table 6 and Figure 5 show about opinion of students regarding issues which are attract by them. They told that almost all issues attract them but religious issue much not gives impact on them.

Table 7: Distribution of Respondents According to Thinking about Media during Reading/ Watching/ Listening Media Text/ Story

Discipline with Respondents Number	Gender	Question(s)/ Queries				
		Who created and why (own or public interest)	Why this attracts attention	May be true or false	Who will be benefited from this you or creator	Media can create bias
Arts 60	M 30	1 (0.56)	2 (1.11)	30 (16.67)	25 (13.89)	30 (16.67)
	F 30	2 (1.11)	3 (1.67)	30 (16.67)	20 (11.11)	30 (16.67)
Commerce 60	M 30	1 (0.56)	1 (0.56)	30 (16.67)	21 (11.67)	30 (16.67)
	F 30	1 (0.56)	0 (0.00)	30 (16.67)	22 (12.22)	30 (16.67)
Science 60	M 30	1 (0.56)	4 (2.22)	30 (16.67)	24 (13.33)	30 (16.67)
	F 30	1 (0.56)	6 (3.33)	30 (16.67)	29 (16.11)	30 (16.67)
Total 180	M 90	3 (1.67)	7 (3.89)	90 (50.00)	70 (38.89)	90 (50.00)
	F 90	4 (2.22)	9 (5.00)	90 (50.00)	71 (39.44)	90 (50.00)
Total 180	M+F 180	7 (3.89)	16 (8.89)	180 (100.00)	141 (78.33)	180 (100.00)

Respondents are allowed to select multiple options

Figure 6: Distribution of Respondents According to Thinking about Media during Reading/ Watching/ Listening Media Text/ Story

From Table 7 and Figure 6, we can understand that students answered, they usually think media story may be true of false, they may not be benefited from these media stories but they do not bother about who created these stories, who will be benefited, etc.

Table 8: Distribution of Respondents about Opinion to Differentiate Information is Reliable or Not

Discipline with Respondents Number	Gender	Differentiate Information Reliability or Not		
		Yes (Can Differentiate)	No (Cannot Differentiate)	Not Possible Always
Arts 60	M 30	4 (2.22)	0 (00.00)	26 (14.44)
	F 30	8 (4.44)	0 (00.00)	22 (12.22)
Commerce 60	M 30	8 (4.44)	0 (00.00)	22 (12.22)
	F 30	1 (0.56)	0 (00.00)	29 (16.11)
Science 60	M 30	11 (6.11)	0 (00.00)	19 (10.56)
	F 30	18 (10.00)	0 (00.00)	12 (6.67)
Total 180	M 90	23 (12.78)	0 (00.00)	67 (37.22)
	F 90	27 (15.00)	0 (00.00)	63 (35.00)

Figure 7: Distribution of Respondents about Opinion to Differentiate Information is Reliable or Not

Table 8 and Figure 7 show that they do not agree that they cannot differentiate the published information is reliable or not. But they admitted that they are not able always to do so.

Table 9: Distribution of Respondents According to Opinion and Thinking about Reason for Incorrect Information

Discipline with Respondents Number	Gender	Opinion About Reason				
		Hurry to broadcast breaking news first	Editorial error	Political pressure	Commercial interest or advertising company pressure	Error during collection from source of information
Arts 60	M 30	13 (7.22)	4 (2.22)	25 (13.89)	10 (5.56)	3 (1.67)
	F 30	21 (11.67)	10 (5.56)	28 (15.56)	21 (11.67)	5 (2.78)
Commerce 60	M 30	19 (10.56)	21 (11.67)	29 (16.11)	17 (9.44)	7 (3.89)
	F 30	12 (6.67)	14 (7.78)	14 (7.78)	10 (5.56)	3 (1.67)
Science 60	M 30	17 (9.44)	8 (4.44)	27 (15.00)	14 (7.78)	6 (3.33)
	F 30	21 (11.67)	2 (1.11)	21 (11.67)	23 (12.78)	2 (1.11)
Total 180	M 90	49 (27.22)	33 (18.33)	81 (45.00)	41 (22.78)	16 (8.89)
	F 90	54 (30.00)	26 (14.44)	63 (35.00)	54 (30.00)	10 (5.56)
Total 180	M+F 180	103 (57.22)	59 (32.78)	144 (80.00)	95 (52.78)	26 (14.44)

Respondents are allowed to select multiple options

Figure 8: Distribution of Respondents According to Opinion and Thinkingabout Reason for Incorrect Information

Table 9 and Figure 8 show that respondents or students mentioned the political pressure; commercial pressure are the main reasons of incorrect information in media.

Table 10: Distribution of Respondents According to Opinion about Media Reporters

Discipline with Respondents Number	Gender	Opinion				
		Reporter gives the fact about story	Put his/her own opinion	Reports go with opinion of majority	Reporter does not clear the original story	Reporter avoid to say detail story
Arts 60	M 30	14 (7.78)	16 (8.89)	21 (11.67)	25 (13.89)	14 (7.78)
	F 30	11 (6.11)	27 (15.00)	25 (13.89)	30 (16.67)	25 (13.89)
Commerce 60	M 30	22 (12.22)	30 (16.67)	22 (12.22)	28 (15.56)	22 (12.22)
	F 30	19 (10.56)	29 (16.11)	23 (12.78)	23 (12.78)	23 (12.78)
Science 60	M 30	18 (10.00)	30 (16.67)	28 (15.56)	30 (16.67)	30 (16.67)
	F 30	21 (11.67)	27 (15.00)	30 (16.67)	24 (13.33)	22 (12.22)
Total 180	M 90	54 (30.00)	76 (42.22)	71 (39.44)	83 (46.11)	66 (36.67)
	F 90	51 (28.33)	83 (46.11)	78 (43.33)	84 (46.67)	70 (38.89)
Total 180	M+F 180	105 (58.33)	159 (88.33)	149 (82.78)	167 (92.78)	136 (75.56)

Respondents are allowed to select multiple options

Figure 9: Distribution of Respondents According to Opinion about Media Reporters

Table 10 and Figure 9 show that respondents give opinion about media reporters. But there is no significant picture. They do not select any particular option. No option gets maximum responses. So, it can be said that they think all options are equally liable. From this table or figure, no single decision cannot be concluded.

Table 11: Distribution of Respondents According to Opinion about Media Fake News

Discipline with Respondents Number	Gender	Aware About Fake News		Detect Fake News		
		Yes	No	Can	Cannot	Not Possible Always
Arts 60	M 30	30 (16.67)	0 (00.00)	1 (0.56)	21 (11.67)	8 (4.44)
	F 30	30 (16.67)	0 (00.00)	0 (00.00)	22 (12.22)	8 (4.44)
Commerce 60	M 30	30 (16.67)	0 (00.00)	0 (00.00)	22 (12.22)	8 (4.44)
	F 30	30 (16.67)	0 (00.00)	0 (00.00)	29 (16.11)	1 (0.56)
Science 60	M 30	30 (16.67)	0 (00.00)	1 (0.56)	19 (10.56)	10 (5.56)
	F 30	30 (16.67)	0 (00.00)	1 (0.56)	12 (6.67)	17 (9.44)
Total 180	M 90	90 (50.00)	0 (00.00)	2 (1.11)	62 (34.44)	26 (14.44)
	F 90	90 (50.00)	0 (00.00)	1 (0.56)	63 (35.00)	26 (14.44)
Total 180	M+F 180	180 (100.00)	0 (0.00)	3 (1.67)	125 (69.44)	52 (28.89)

Respondents are allowed to select multiple options

Figure 10: Distribution of Respondents According to Opinion about Media Fake News

From table 11 and figure 10, we can see that the students said that they are aware about fake news but they cannot detect these always as fake or not.

Table 12: Distribution of Respondents about Expressed Own Opinion in Any Media Platform

Discipline with Respondents Number	Gender	Issue				
		Educational Issue	Political Issue	Social Issue	Cultural Issue	Economic Issue
Arts 60	M 30	5 (2.78)	27 (15.00)	22 (12.22)	8 (4.44)	2 (1.11)
	F 30	12 (6.67)	5 (2.78)	10 (5.56)	6 (3.33)	1 (0.56)
Commerce 60	M 30	18 (10.00)	22 (12.22)	29 (16.11)	12 (6.67)	15 (8.33)
	F 30	6 (3.33)	12 (6.67)	26 (14.44)	25 (13.89)	8 (4.44)
Science 60	M 30	19 (10.56)	28 (15.56)	22 (12.22)	16 (8.89)	6 (3.33)
	F 30	22 (12.22)	14 (7.78)	28 (15.56)	29 (16.11)	2 (1.11)
Total 180	M 90	42 (23.33)	77 (42.78)	73 (40.56)	36 (20.00)	23 (12.78)
	F 90	40 (22.22)	31 (17.22)	64 (35.56)	60 (33.33)	11 (6.11)
Total 180	M+F 180	82 (45.56)	108 (60.00)	137 (76.11)	96 (53.33)	34 (18.89)

Respondents are allowed to select multiple options

Figure 11: Distribution of Respondents about Media Expressed Own Opinion in Any Media Platform

Table 12 and Figure 11 show that the students have expressed own opinion in media platform. They select almost all options but economic issue may be ignored or overlooked by them.

Table 13: Activities Performed or Participation in Media

Discipline with Respondents Number	Gender	Activity		
		Write letter to media organisation or editor for correction of news or information	Create own news stories and send to media house	Ask any question to clarify information
Arts 60	M 30	3 (1.67)	20 (11.11)	29 (16.11)
	F 30	5 (2.78)	29 (16.11)	30 (16.67)
Commerce 60	M 30	2 (1.11)	15 (8.33)	27 (15.00)
	F 30	1 (0.56)	22 (12.22)	29 (16.11)
Science 60	M 30	9 (5.00)	29 (16.11)	30 (16.67)
	F 30	2 (1.67)	28 (15.56)	30 (16.67)
Total 180	M 90	14 (7.78)	64 (35.56)	86 (47.78)
	F 90	8 (4.44)	79 (43.89)	89 (49.44)
Total 180	M+F 180	22 (12.22)	143 (79.44)	175 (97.22)

Respondents are allowed to select multiple options

Figure 12: Activities Performed or Participation in Media

From Table 13 and Figure 12, we can see that maximum number of respondents said that when they have understood that any news or information is wrong, then they have ignored it, do not feel any necessity for correction. Rest of them said that they have send letter to editors of newspapers in two or three times.

They said that they have create news about road accidents, bad condition of local village road, bad condition of school building, etc. and post on social media platform. They said that they have raised question to clarify information only on social media.

Table 14: Distribution of Respondents about Media Literacy Training/ Education

Discipline with Respondents Number	Gender	Opinion		
		Media Literacy Training/ Education can empower students by developing responsible digital citizenship (awareness about IPR, copyright laws etc.)	Media Literacy Training/ Education empowers to critical thinking (awareness about reliable sources, credible news, cross-referencing)	Media Literacy Training/ Education can prepare students for global communication
Arts 60	M 30	23 (12.78)	28 (15.56)	22 (12.22)
	F 30	29 (16.11)	30 (16.67)	26 (14.44)
Commerce 60	M 30	30 (16.67)	29 (16.11)	23 (12.78)
	F 30	29 (16.11)	27 (15.00)	29 (16.11)
Science 60	M 30	30 (16.67)	30 (16.67)	29 (16.11)
	F 30	30 (16.67)	29 (16.11)	30 (16.67)
Total 180	M 90	83 (46.11)	87 (48.33)	74 (41.11)
	F 90	88 (48.89)	86 (47.78)	85 (47.22)
Total 180	M+F 180	171 (95.00)	173 (96.11)	159 (88.33)

Respondents are allowed to select multiple options

Figure 13: Distribution of Respondents about Media Literacy Training/ Education

Table 14 and Figure 13 shows that they remarked that media literacy training can empower students but media literacy is not only one factor for global communication.

Table 15: Distribution of Respondents regarding Opinion about Activities of Library

Discipline with Respondents Number	Gender	Opinion				
		Dependent on college library to get information	Adequate electronic resources	Satisfactory staff cooperation	Librarians help for develop IT skill	Librarians help to grow media literacy
Arts 60	M 30	29 (16.11)	25 (13.89)	22 (12.22)	29 (16.11)	10 (5.56)
	F 30	30 (16.67)	22 (12.22)	15 (8.33)	29 (16.11)	12 (6.67)
Commerce 60	M 30	15 (8.33)	19 (10.56)	21 (11.67)	19 (10.56)	15 (8.33)
	F 30	10 (5.56)	23 (12.78)	14 (7.78)	22 (12.22)	13 (7.22)
Science 60	M 30	21 (11.62)	21 (11.67)	10 (5.56)	24 (13.33)	20 (11.11)
	F 30	15 (8.33)	17 (9.44)	17 (9.44)	30 (16.67)	18 (10.00)
Total 180	M 90	65 (36.11)	65 (36.11)	53 (29.44)	72 (40.00)	45 (25.00)
	F 90	55 (30.56)	62 (34.44)	46 (25.56)	81 (45.00)	42 (23.33)
Total 180	M+F 180	120 (66.67)	127 (70.56)	99 (55.00)	153 (85.00)	87 (48.33)

Respondents are allowed to select multiple options

Figure 14: Distribution of Respondents regarding Opinion about Activities of Library

Table 15 and Figure 14 shows that they are using college library but are not dependent on college library because they are also member of other public libraries. They also admitted that librarians of this college are trying to grow awareness about new technologies, about IT skill, and about media literacy also.

7. Findings of the Study

- From this study, it is clear that the majority of the respondents/ students spend more time in social media, but in question of reliability, they still depend on newspapers and on TV reports.
- They said that they gathered their required information from local club to classroom, from friend circle to library. They enjoy each and every information from all places.
- They told that local, regional, national and also international issues attracted their attention. Filmly or funny videos also attracted their attention – way to spend leisure time.

- They admitted that they mainly expressed their own opinion towards social and political issues. educational issues and economic issues are neglected.
- Most of the all-respondents students think about who created the media story, who will be benefited from this story, etc. during reading media text or story.
- Students admitted that they cannot always differentiate a particular information reliable or not.
- The opinion about incorrect information in media, students express the reasons as hurry to broadcast and political pressure only. They cannot agree to editorial error, error during information collection, etc.
- Students also give opinion about media reports, those reports put their own opinion in media stories.
- About fake news, students said that they are aware about fake news but cannot detect always as it is fake.
- Participation in media of the respondents/ students is very low.
- Students go with that media literacy training can give them empowerment and help to prepare for the global community.
- Lastly, the students said that Vidyanagar College Library gave them training for media literacy.

On the other side, Vidyanagar College Library authority said that they cannot able to arrange or organize regular formal training programs about media literacy, but the librarians try to help the students every time during searching.

7.1 Interpretation or Summery

- This study reveals some contradictory views. From daily observation, it is reflected that students are still dependent on print media for their syllabus-based study. But they said that they collected more information from TV and newspaper. Library is one of the most information sources. But their responses placed the library in third position after TV and newspaper. It is only possible when they may differentiate educational information with other information.

- This study finds another contradictory view i.e. students said that they are aware that media information literacy can improve their critical thinking. They also said that the library can grow media information literacy and can help them for this. But they are not willing to depend on the library. It is only possible when the students received any negative behavior from library or for any other reasons, they are not feeling interest from library.
- Third contradictory view can be found by personal observation. In this study, students said that they are aware about fake information as well as copyright issues, etc. But in the practical scenario, they are habituated with copy-paste culture during submission of classroom assignments. Related faculty members and librarians are worried about this practice. Because students are doing this in the library premises also. Only regular monitoring can minimize this bad habit.
- Another most important and interesting contradictory is that they are aware about fake news, fake information circulated from electronic media, especially from social media. But in this research paper, students said that they are attracted and feeling interest and also spend more time on social media. It is possible when either they are using these platforms for spending their leisure time, or they can ignore all of this information i.e. this information has no impact on them.

8. Future Strategies

Principal of the Vidyanagar College spend almost all office-time in thinking of students' skill development. On behalf of the principal, librarians of the Vidyanagar College Library are trying to arrange visits to media houses among interested students during summer or winter recess without hampering the regular academic calendar. Students can take practical knowledge and experiences how a news report can be created from an incident. It is now at the extreme primary level. Because taking consent from guardians, arrange permission and approval from different stages will be time-consuming and troublesome.

This college is trying to arrange special lecture or training by owners of media houses and reporters as a resource person that may help the students to grow awareness about media literacy.

9. Recommendations

Strategies are to be taken by college and college library to raise awareness among students about the importance of media literacy by organising seminars, workshops, etc.

- Library should make easy access by growing the number of online resources and digital infrastructure.
- Library should provide regular training programs for enhance technical skill, should aware about media ethics, peoples' rights, etc. Quiz programme and debates can also be organised regarding media issues.
- Library should alert the students about the wrong application of AI technologies, fake news, deepfake, authors' credentials, online safety etc.
- On behalf of college, it can be suggested that faculty members should start lecture about media literacy for discussion in the class.
- With collaboration and cooperation of students, teaching and non-teaching staff of this college along with librarians, can create discussion platform at their own level for spreading the necessity and importance of media literacy.
- Digital dependency of students is resulting stop to depend on own thinking by duplicating internet content. To stop this, faculty members should check students' assignments by using modern anti-plagiarism tools. They should return to the students if it is below standard to use their own thinking of students, which will enhance quality of creativity. By this effort, students can learn how to handle the digital media information for their study purpose.

These are some related suggestions that can be implemented with minimum budget and with other limitations by administrators of this college and authority of the college library.

10. Conclusion

At end of this paper, after compare the objectives of this study with results of analysis part, it can be concluded that in Vidyanagar College Library, students of Vidyanagar College are preferred to use newspapers as print media, TV and social media, etc. as electronic media to get required information. Less than 50% of respondents can differentiate a particular information is reliable or not.

In question of fake news, nearly fifty percent respondents have not enough knowledge to detect an information as fake or not. So, level of media literacy is not up to the mark.

Vidyanagar College Library is trying to change the present scenarios. Hope improvements will be come to light by conducting further studies in future.

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